

FINANCIAL INSTITUTION STABILITY AND INVESTMENT IN SUB-SAHARAN AFRICA

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Abstract: Investment is considered a strategy for creating jobs, and reducing poverty in many economies. SSA's financial stability (FS) is still low and cannot be compared to that of the world's industrialized nations. This research proposed to investigate the impact of the financial institution stability (FIS) (bank based stability) on investment in SSA. The study employed pooled mean group autoregressive distribution lag to analyze the data and discovered that both PRI and PBI in SSA cannot be explained by financial stability both in the short and long run at any of the conventional levels of statistical significance. In the long run, variables found to be significant include: EXD, and DS. This suggests that EXD has a negative influence on PRI at the 1% significance level; DS has a positive influence on PRI at the 5% level of significance, indicate that an increase in DS causes PRI to increase. According to the report, financial institutions should strive for capital sufficiency, and regulatory bodies should keep an eye on it. To encourage investment, regulatory bodies should make sure that these institutions' capital base is sufficient to meet their risk profile.

Keywords: bank based debt, financial stability, private investment, public investment.

INTRODUCTION

Investment is cost incurred with expectation of increasing wealth. Investment is an asset that appreciates in value and generates flexible income to investors. It enhances production of good and service which lead to economic growth and development. A nation with stable investment the standard of living is improving. It stimulates innovation, raises living standards, generates employment, and establishes the institutional and structural underpinnings required for long-term growth (Mirzaev, 2020).

Investments may come from public or private sources. Investments from the public and private sectors are essential to production functions because they supply the funds needed for growth (Ibrahim & Muammer, 2020). The motive of Private Investment (PRI) is to maximize expected return and minimize risk, while Public Investment (PBI) is targeted at improving citizens' living standard.

Naceur et al. (2017) opined that risks and returns can be viewed as a trade-off that determines financial stability. Financial system soundness and stability are important markers of FD. Z-scores, to the ratio of net foreign exchange capital and asset quality, liquidity, and capital adequacy (CA), among others, are some of the indicators of financial stability used by financial institutions. Similarly, financial market indicators of financial

stability include stock price index volatility (standard deviation/average), sovereign bond index volatility (skewness), sensitivity to earnings manipulation, and ratio of price to earnings.

Financial stability information shows that SSA's financial system performs worse than other regions of the world. For example, WDI (2020) data shows that the financial stability proxy of assets quality in SSA's financial system is 17.51%, which is lower than those of countries such as Solomon Islands (93%), Sudan (94.8%), and Afghanistan (86.9%). A stable financial system and development are expected to guarantee sustainable investment. Given the low degree of financial stability in SSA's financial system, it is expected that the contribution to which extent FD has affected investment in SSA remained in the dark. This forms the thought of this paper.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Keynesian Theory of Investment

British economist John Maynard Keynes introduced the Keynesian theory of investment in his seminal work "The General Theory of Employment, Interest and Money" (1936). This theory established the groundwork for macroeconomic theory in the 20th century and posed a challenge to classical economics. Keynes maintained that expectations of future profitability—what he dubbed the marginal efficiency of capital, or MEC—are just as important in motivating investment as interest rates. According to the hypothesis, changes in business expectations—often referred to as "animal spirits"—have an impact on investment, making it unstable and volatile. Comparing the MEC and interest rate is essential when making investment selections. Investment rises if $MEC > \text{interest rate}$; if $MEC < \text{interest rate}$, investment falls (Blinder, 2008; Samuelson & Nordhaus 2010; Dornbusch, Fischer & Startz 2013).

The assumption is that the predicted rate of return above an investment's cost is known as the marginal efficiency of capital. When the MEC is higher than or equivalent to the interest rate, businesses make investments. Assuming expectations stay the same, investment rises when interest rates decline. According to Keynes, a lower interest rate lowers borrowing costs and promotes greater investment. But he also underlined that uncertainty makes investments less sensitive to interest rates. Business expectations regarding future profitability have an impact on investment decisions. Keynes maintained that animal spirits (psychological aspects and confidence) had a significant impact on investment decisions due to the unpredictability of the future. Investment becomes unstable and volatile as a result. By adjusting interest rates, Keynes did not make the assumption that savings always equated to investment, in contrast to classical theory. Rather, income is adjusted to match investment and saving. Investment is regarded as exogenous, meaning it is not exclusively based on current revenue. Income and employment are multiplied by changes in investment (Dornbusch, Fischer, & Startz 2013; Blanchard & Johnson 2017; Samuelson & Nordhaus 2010; Keynes 1936).

John Maynard Keynes's *The General Theory of Employment, Interest and Money* (1936) contains criticisms of the Keynesian theory of investment, which highlights how interest rates and business expectations—also known as "animal spirits"—affect the amount of money invested. Despite being fundamental to contemporary macroeconomics, the theory has drawn a lot of criticism throughout the years. Keynes believed that higher levels of investment would result from lower interest rates. However, detractors contend that in practice, market conditions, technical advancements, and expectations for future profitability have a considerably greater influence on investment decisions than do slight variations in interest rates. "The complexity of real-world investment decisions, which frequently depend more on expectations and profitability than on borrowing costs, is overlooked by the Keynesian focus on interest rates as the primary determinant of investment" (Blanchard

&Johnson 2013). Fundamentally demand-driven, Keynesian theory frequently downplays the significance of supply-side variables including institutional characteristics, worker productivity, and technological innovation. These elements, according to critics, are essential in determining long-term investment behavior. Keynesian theory works well for understanding short-term changes in investment, but it is not as strong over the long term. Keynes downplayed the importance of productivity gains and capital accumulation for long-term economic growth; whereas neoclassical growth models like the Solow-Swan model highlight these aspects. Keynes coined the term "animal spirits" to describe the emotional and psychological aspects of investment behavior. Despite its insightfulness, this idea is not empirically precise, which makes it challenging to model or quantify in real-world macroeconomic analysis (Mankiw 2019). Contrary to what Keynesian theory would have us believe, a number of actual studies indicate that investment does not always react strongly to fluctuations in interest rates. For instance, interest rates dropped to almost zero in several developed economies following the 2008 financial crisis, yet investment growth remained slow, suggesting that other factors were at work.

Enhancements in the scale, effectiveness, and depth of financial markets and institutions are referred to as FD. Effectively mobilize and distribute funds, lower transaction and information costs, control risks, and encourage investment and innovation are all characteristics of well-developed financial systems (Levine 2005). Keynes highlighted how susceptible investments are to changes in interest rates. This channel is impacted by FD in two ways: Better financial intermediation guarantees that interest rates reflect real risk and time preferences, while efficient financial systems lower borrowing costs. Investment is unpredictable and motivated by expectations, according to Keynesian theory; FD gives businesses access to a range of funding sources, such as bonds, stock, and loans. Increase investor trust by lowering reliance on internal funding and providing risk management tools (Aghion, Bacchetta, & Banerjee, 2005). Keynesians contend that investment multiplies production. By facilitating the reallocation of capital to productive sectors and enabling greater economic involvement through financial inclusion, FD intensifies this effect (De Gregorio & Guidotti 1995). A plethora of empirical research, including King and Levine (1993) and Beck, Levine, and Loayza (2000), bolsters the notion that FD improves macroeconomic stability and increases investment responsiveness to interest rate fluctuations.

Empirically, Leesi, (2025) stated that the real sector investment of Nigerian quoted commercial banks is not significantly impacted by the Tier One capital ratio. Investment in the real sector is not significantly impacted by the tier two capital ratio. The listed commercial banks' real sector investment is positively and significantly impacted by capital to total loans. The listed commercial banks' real sector investment is positively impacted by capital to total deposits, but not significantly. The degree of openness of the economy recorded a positive and significant impact on private investment (Francis & Ismail, 2021), contrary openness of the economy have positive and insignificant effect (Fortune & Charles, 2019). Real exchange rate has recorded a negative and significant impact on private investment in the long and short run (Francis & Ismail, 2021; Agbarakwe, 2019 and Fortune & Charles, 2019). Broad money supply negatively and significantly influences domestic investment (Chimere, Simplice, Kingsley, & Patrick, 2020), contrary Private investment is positively affected by broad money (thuy, Anh, & Diem, 2020; George & Nneka, 2019 and Dayo & Kemi, 2013). The turnover ratio had a negative and significant impact on investment growth (Idowu & Mercy, 2020). Contrary, the effect of turnover ratio on investment is insignificant (Roseline & Esman, 2011). There is uni-directional causality from stock market development to investment amount. There is also uni-directional causality from investment amount to banking sector development (Banu, 2016; In contrary private investment and gross investment have a bidirectional causal relation with financial development (Saban, Abdullah, & Murat, 2009). Inflation rate (INF)

at current period has negative and significant impact on investment in Nigeria (Agbarakwe, 2019 and Fortune & Charles, 2019).

METHODOLOGY

Model Specification

Since the WDI and IMF do not have data on financial stability index, these models are developed independently to determine how investment is affected by financial stability. The research uses Asset quality as a proxy for financial stability, to measure its effect on investment. The data available is from 2004 to 2021.

$$PRI = f (FS, INF, LNOER, LNGDP, EXD, DS) \quad (3.1)$$

$$PRI = f (FS, INF, LNOER, LNGDP, EXD, DS) \quad (3.2)$$

A priori expectation

Models3 & 4: $\beta_1, >1$

Where

PRI: Private investment

PBI: Public investment

FS: Financial Stability

INF: Inflation

LNOER: Log of official exchange rate

LNGDP: Log of gross domestic product

EXD: External debt

DS: Debt servicing

Model III: Financial stability and PRI

$$PRI_{it} = \beta_0 + \sum_{m=1}^M \beta_{1n} PRI_{it-m} + \sum_{n=0}^N \beta_{2n} FS_{it-n} + \sum_{n=0}^N \beta_{3n} INF_{it-n} + \sum_{n=0}^N \beta_{4n} LNOER_{it-n} + \sum_{n=0}^N \beta_{5n} LNGDP_{it-n} + \sum_{n=0}^N \beta_{6n} EXD_{it-n} + \sum_{n=0}^N \beta_{7n} DS_{it-n} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (3.3)$$

Model IV: Financial stability and PBI

$$PBI_{it} = \beta_0 + \sum_{m=1}^M \beta_{1n} PBI_{it-m} + \sum_{n=0}^N \beta_{2n} FS_{it-n} + \sum_{n=0}^N \beta_{3n} INF_{it-n} + \sum_{n=0}^N \beta_{4n} LNOER_{it-n} + \sum_{n=0}^N \beta_{5n} LNGDP_{it-n} + \sum_{n=0}^N \beta_{6n} EXD_{it-n} + \sum_{n=0}^N \beta_{7n} DS_{it-n} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (3.4)$$

Where

β : Constant term

ε : Error term

β_0 - β_{13} : The explanatory variables' parameters

t: Time period

i: Private and public investment of countries involved

Estimation Technique

The data is analyzed via both descriptive analysis and inferential analysis. Unit root tests are conducted to estimate the variables' stationarity. The regression model is then estimated via PMG/ARDL to ascertain how FD affects investment. The MG/PMG/ARDL estimation methods are used in this investigation, because they involve both pooling and averaging. They permit the intercepts, short-run coefficients, and error variations to vary freely between groups. However, they constrain the long-run coefficients to be the same.

The primary estimation methods used in dynamic heterogeneous models include the mean group (MG), pooled mean group (PMG), and dynamic fixed effects (DFE) estimators. Diverse slope coefficients are supported by

the MG estimator, which first computes time series regressions at the individual level before averaging the coefficients. The PMG estimator can be conceptualized as a blend of pooled and heterogenous estimations, allowing heterogeneity in the short run but imposing homogeneity in the long run (Abdulkadir, 2022; Blackburne& Frank, 2007; Ditzen, 2018). Since the DFE estimations are probably biased when short-term coefficients vary between units, as discussed in Pesaran and Smith (1995),it is not used in this investigation.

The Hausman (1978) test is a useful tool for verifying the homogeneity of long-term coefficients. This test is based on the null hypothesis that no consistent variations exist among the coefficients. When the null hypothesis is accepted, the PMG estimator—which was put forth by Arnold et al. (2011)—is more effective than the MG estimator. When confirming the homogeneity of long-term coefficients, the PMG estimator's greater efficiency over the MG estimator must be taken into account.

PRESENTATION AND DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

This section reports and interprets the results obtained from the statistical analyses carried out. Specifically, the methods used include descriptive analysis, correlation analysis, unit root test and PMG.

Table 4.1: Descriptive Statistics (Models I and II)

Variables	Mean	Median	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
PRI	23.6510	21.9677	7.0560	12.4001	39.7264
PBI	2.4473	2.2522	1.6380	0.0000	6.8747
CA	9.0452	10.0408	5.5444	0.0000	22.6000
IF	7.7670	6.9119	5.0452	-1.1069	26.2398
LNGDP	24.5520	24.2903	1.2765	22.5512	27.0762
LNOER	3.8776	4.3484	2.143560	-0.1059	7.7397
EXD	49.7870	40.6134	31.6366	3.8950	31.6366
DS	10.4849	7.0523	9.6003	0.6286	43.3283

Source: Author’s computation (2025)

4.1 Descriptive Statistics

With a mean value of 23.6510, the result shows that overall PRI disclosures in the chosen countries are not very strong. The data are regularly distributed around the mean, as evidenced by the narrow range between the mean value of 23.6510 and the median value of 21.9677. The maximum value of 39.7264 and the minimum value of 12.4001show a substantial disparity, indicating a high degree of variation across the chosen nations. The Std. Dev. of 7.0560 shows a considerable degree of volatility in the PRI disclosure for the chosen countries.

With an average value of 2.4473the result reveals that overall PBI disclosures in the chosen nations are extremely low. The data appear to be regularly distributed around the mean, as indicated by the narrow range between the mean values of 2.4473and the median value of 2.2522. The considerable disparity between the maximum values of 6.8747and the minimum value of 0.0000 suggests that there is little variation among the chosen nations. The disclosed PBI of the chosen countries exhibits a notable degree of volatility, as indicated by the Std. Dev. of 1.6380.

The average value of 9.0452 indicates that overall CA disclosures from the selected countries are rather moderate. The data appear to be regularly distributed around the mean, as indicated by the narrow range between the mean values of 9.0452and the median value of 10.0408. The minimal value of 0.0000 and the maximum value of 22.6000, which range significantly, show that there is little variation across the chosen

Variables	CA	INF	LNGDP	LNOER	EXD	DS
CA	1.0000					
INF	0.2025***	1.0000				
LNGDP	-0.0533	0.0271	1.0000			
LNOER	-0.2032***	-0.2989***	0.1160*	1.0000		
EXD	0.3189***	0.2616***	0.1033	0.1331	1.0000	
DS	0.3628***	-0.1696***	-0.0493	0.0656	0.1160*	1.0000

nations. The disclosed CA of the chosen countries exhibits a considerable degree of volatility, as indicated by the Std. Dev. of 5.5444.

The average value of 7.7670 indicates that overall INF disclosures from the selected countries are rather moderate. The data appear to be regularly distributed around the mean, as indicated by the narrow range between the mean value of 7.7670 and the median value of 6.9119. The minimal value of -1.1069 and the maximum value of 26.2398, which range significantly, show that there is little variety across the chosen nations. The disclosed INF of the chosen countries exhibits a considerable degree of volatility, as indicated by the Std. Dev. of 5.0452.

The average value of 24.5520 suggests that overall LNGDP disclosures from the selected countries are fairly moderate. The data appear to be regularly distributed around the mean, as indicated by the narrow range between the mean value of 24.5520 and the median value of 24.2903. The minimal value of 22.5512 and the maximum value of 27.0762 show a low degree of variance across the chosen nations, as do the considerable disparity between them. The disclosed LNGDP of the chosen countries exhibits a notable degree of volatility, as indicated by the Std. Dev. of 1.2765.

The average value of 3.8776 indicates that overall LNOER disclosures from the selected countries are rather modest. The data are often distributed about the mean, as seen by the narrow range between the mean value of 3.8776 and the median value of 4.3484. Significant variations exist across the chosen countries, as evidenced by the max value of 7.7397 and the min value of -0.1059. The Std. Dev. of 2.1436 suggests that there is a considerable degree of volatility in the LNOER disclosure for the chosen countries.

The average value of 49.7870 suggests that overall EXD disclosures from the selected countries are relatively high. The data appear to be regularly distributed around the mean, as indicated by the narrow range between the mean value of 49.7870 and the median value of 40.6134. Significant variations exist among the chosen countries, as evidenced by the discrepancy between the max value of 31.6366 and the min value of 3.8950. The Std. Dev. of 31.6366 suggests a substantial amount of volatility in the EXD disclosure of the selected nations.

The average value of 10.4849 indicates that overall SD disclosures from the selected countries are quite low. The data appear to be regularly distributed around the mean, as indicated by the narrow range between the mean value of 10.4849 and the median value of 7.0523. Significant variations exist among the chosen countries, as evidenced by the discrepancy between the max values of 43.3283 and the min value of 0.6286. A considerable degree of volatility in the disclosure of the selected nations' SD is shown by the Std. Dev. of 9.6003.

Table 4.2: Correlation Analysis (Models I and II)

Source: Author’s computation (2025)

4.2 Multicollinearity Test

Table 4.2 displays the results of the correlation analysis, which indicates that the following variables have low positive correlations with CA: DS, EXD, INF, LNGDP, and LNOER. On the other hand, LNGDP and LNOER

have low negative correlations with CA. EXD and INF exhibit low positive and negative associations with DS respectively, while INF has a low positive correlation with EXD, and LNOER has a positive correlation with LNGDP. All these results are statistically significant. The multicollinearity test is passed by the model since the correlation analysis result shows that there is no linear dependence between any of the variables.

Table 4.3 Variation Inflation Factor (Models I and II)

Variables	VIF	1/VIF
EXD	1.58	0.6341
DS	1.54	0.6497
INF	1.41	0.7068
CA	1.33	0.7537
LNOER	1.24	0.8081
LNGDP	1.03	0.9662
Mean VIF	1.36	

Source: Author’s computation (2025)

4.3 Variance inflation factors

When there is evidence of a robust linear correlation between the explanatory variables in a regression model, multicollinearity problems arise. One technique to gauge the level of multicollinearity among the model variables is to use VIFs. To prove that the explanatory variables are not extremely collinear, the value for each one should not be greater than 10, according to the VIF test. According to Gujarati (2007), the tolerance level (1/VIF) should be closer to one and the VIF test result should be less than five if the variables are not highly collinear. The independent variables in the regression model have a VIF value of less than five, as indicated by the VIF outcome displayed in Table 4.3. When the tolerance threshold is closer to zero, it means that multicollinearity will not have a major negative impact on the model. While there is no correlation between EXD, DS, INF, CA, LNOER, and LNGDP and other explanatory factors in the models, multicollinearity is absent.

Table 4.4. Panel Unit Root Test (Models I and II)

Variables	IPS test	Fisher-PP test	Level
PRI	-3.6828*** (0.0001)	6.6966*** (0.0000)	I(1)
PBI	-1.1685*** (0.0000)	6.1561*** (0.0000)	I(1)
CA	-3.6493*** (0.0001)	7.5876*** (0.0000)	I(1)
INF	-4.3225*** (0.0000)	8.4424 *** (0.0000)	I(0)
LNGDP	-1.8363 *** (0.0332)	4.1590 *** (0.0000)	I(0)
LNOER	-2.6584 *** (0.0039)	3.4259*** (0.0003)	I(0)
EXD	-4.8178 (0.0000)	21.4881 (0.0000)	I(0)

SD	-6.6057 (0.0000)	15.3811 (0.0000)	I(1)
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Source: Author’s computation (2025)

Note: Automatic lag selection is based on the Bayesian Information Criterion.

P-values are reported in brackets.

*** indicates significance at 1%.

4.4 Panel unit root test

The IPS and Fisher-type (ADF tests) unit root test results are displayed in Table 4.4. According to the findings, PBI, PRI, CA, LNOER, and DS are stationary at first difference, or integrated of order one (I(1)), but INF, EXD, and LNGDP are stationary at level or integrated of order zero (I(0)). The investigation continues by using the PMG and MG techniques provided by Pesaran and Smith (1995) to assess the long- and short-run correlations because the results indicate a mixture of I(0) and I(1). The Hausman test is then used to see how heterogeneity affects the average values of the coefficients. It tests the null hypothesis of homogeneity based on the comparison between the MG and PMG estimators.

Table 4.5a. HausmanTest (Models III)

Variables	(b) Mg	(B) Pmg	(b-B) Deference	sqrt(diag(V_b-V_B)) S.E.
CA	1.6939	-0.0675	1.7614	3.9245
INF	0.9905	-0.0982	1.0887	2.3929
LNOER	-18.4073	5.2054	-23.6127	59.6308
LNGDP	8.9239	5.5051	3.4188	34.9446
EXD	-0.0465	-0.0928	0.0463	1.1688
DS	3.0661	-0.1959	3.2620	10.1266

Source: Author’s computation (2025) “

b = consistent under Ho and Ha; obtained from xtpmg

B = inconsistent under Ha, efficient under Ho; obtained from xtpmg

Test: Ho: difference in coefficients not systematic

chi2 (10) = (b-B)'[(V_b-V_B) ^ (-1)] (b-B) = 1.59

Prob>chi2 = 0.9531

Table 4.5b. Hausman Test (Models IV)

Variables	(b) Mg	(B) Pmg	(b-B) Deference	sqrt(diag(V_b-V_B)) S.E.
CA	-0.0348	-0.0095	-0.0253	0.2319
INF	0.1463	0.0591	0.0872	0.2823
LNOER	1.3193	1.2110	0.1083	14.3497
LNGDP	0.4762	-0.3207	0.7969	4.1274
EXD	0.0699	-0.0018	0.0717	0.2299
DS	0.8848	-0.0257	0.9104	2.9625

Source: Author’s computation (2025)

b = consistent under Ho and Ha; obtained from xtpmg

B = inconsistent under Ha, efficient under Ho; obtained from xtpmg

Test: Ho: difference in coefficients not systematic

chi2 (10) = (b-B)'[(V_b-V_B) ^ (-1)] (b-B) = 0.76

Prob>chi2 = 0.9932

The result of the comparison between the MG and PMG estimators shows that PMG is more efficient. Given that in Models I and II, the p-value is more than 0.05 (0.9531 and 0.9932) in both PRI and PBI, the null hypothesis cannot be ruled out.

Table 4.6 Pooled mean group estimates (all sampled countries) (Model I)

Variables	Model I DV = PRI	
	Long-run coefficient (all sampled countries)	Short-run coefficient (all sampled countries)
CA	-0.0675 (0.1154)	0.0669 (0.3036)
INF	-0.0982 (0.0969)	0.1669 (0.1208)
LNOER	5.2054*** (1.3312)	1.5133 (8.2273)
LNGDP	5.5051*** (1.0299)	15.69804*** (6.9140)
EXD	-0.0928*** (0.0163)	0.2087 (0.1512)
DS	-0.1959*** (0.0495)	0.5247 (0.4274)
Observations	153	153

Source: Author’s computation (2025)

Note: The values in parentheses denote the standard error.

***, **, and * indicate significance at 1%, 5%, and 10% respectively.

4.13 Interpretation of Result for Model I

Findings from the pooled estimates (Table 4.6) show that all explanatory variables (except LNGDP) are insignificant in explaining PRI in the short term; LNGDP has a favourable impact on PRI at the 5% significance level, with a p-value (0.023) and coefficient (15.69804). This suggests that a unit increase in LNGDP increases PRI by 0.157% in the short run. This finding is consistent with that of George and Nneka (2019). In the long run LNGDP has a favourable influence on PRI at the 1% significance level, with a p-value (0.000) and coefficient (5.5051). This suggests that a unit increase in LNGDP raises PRI by 0.055%.

In the long range, LNOER has a positive impact on PRI at the 1% significance level, with a p-value (0.000) and coefficient (5.2054). This indicates that an increase in LNOER raises PRI by 0.052%. EXD has an adverse influence on PRI at a significance level of 1%, with a coefficient (-0.0928) and a p-value (0.000). This suggests an increase in EXD decreases PRI by 0.09%. DS has an adverse influence on PRI at the 1% level of

significance, with a coefficient (-0.1959) and a p-value (0.000). This suggests an increase in DS decreases PRI by 0.019%.

Table 4.7 Pooled mean group estimates (all sampled countries) (Model IV)

Variables	Model IV DV = PBI	
	Long-run coefficient (all sampled countries)	Short-run coefficient (all sampled countries)
CA	-0.0095 (0.0272)	-0.0188 (0.0331)
INF	0.0591*** (0.0131)	-0.0344 (0.0228)
LNOER	1.2110*** (0.2201)	-0.1738 (2.8962)
LNGDP	-0.3207*** (0.1140)	-2.13667 (2.7233)
EXD	-0.0018 (0.0034)	-0.0044 (0.0152)
DS	-0.0257*** (0.0078)	-0.0257 (0.0643)
Observations	153	153

Source: Author's computation (2025)

Note: The values in parentheses denote the standard error.

***, **, and * indicate significance at 1%, 5%, and 10% respectively.

4.14 Interpretation of Result for Model II

According to the pooled estimates results (Table 4.7), PBI in SSA cannot be explained by any of the explanatory factors in the short run. In the long run, variables found to be significant include: INF, LNOER, LNGDP, and DS. INF has a positive influence on PBI at the 1% level of significance, with a p-value (0.000) and coefficient (0.0591). This indicates that an increase in INF increases PBI by 0.0591%.

LNOER has a favourable impact on PBI at the 1% level of significance, with a p-value (0.000) and coefficient (1.2110). This indicates that an increase in LNOER increases PRI by 1.2110%. LNGDP has an adverse influence on PBI at the 1% significance level, with a coefficient (-0.3207) and a p-value (0.005). This indicates that an increase in LNGDP decreases PBI by -0.03207%. DS has a favourable influence on PBI at the 1% significance level, with a coefficient (-0.0257) and a p-value (0.001). This suggests that an increase in DS decreases PBI by -0.026%.

Findings of the study reveal that stability of financial institutions is irrelevant in determining investment (PBI/PRI) in the sampled countries. This result is applicable to both the near term and the overtime. This finding is in line with the work of Leesi, (2025), insignificant results obtained for financial stability may be attributed to insufficiency of capital base of financial institutions in SSA to meet up with the demand of investors. This outcome is in contrast with both the a priori expectation and the endogenous growth theory.

Conclusion and Recommendation

The lack of current research on the relationship between FIS and investment in SSA made this study necessary. The study's time frame is restricted to 42 years (1980–2021) because data for 2022 and 2024 were not available. Financial institution stability has no bearing on short- and long-term investment decisions (PBI and PRI). The paper goes on to say that INF, EXD, and DS are significant variables that may account for both PRI and PBI in the SSA nations that were sampled. According to the report the study recommended that, financial institutions should strive for capital sufficiency, and regulatory bodies should keep an eye on it. To encourage investment, regulatory bodies should make sure that these institutions' capital base is sufficient to meet their risk profile. Future research can take into account indicators of market-based financial stability as data availability increases within SSA. The analysis of financial stability (one of the FD indicators) is restricted to banks and does not extend to markets due to non-availability of data.

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